

Part of

Data management plan for RTU-PA-2024/1-0032 project
“Sustainable Model Design for Conceptual System and Lexical
Framework Pliancy Analysis for Perceptual Data Processing of
the Pre-school Age Actors”

Description

LCS FARP

Description

The data will be collected through (1) observations of pre-school age actors' use of language; (2) unstructured surveys; (3) comparative multimodal analysis of artifacts created by the pre-school age actors alongside the verbal data acquired in course of observations.

Recommendations will be developed for the development of learning materials and activities for pre-school age actors based on the awareness of their perception system.

Researchers

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Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Consolidation grant

Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

1. To make observations in pre-school institutions of children's use of language and understanding of concepts by taking detailed notes on pre-school age actors' language use, including vocabulary, sentence structure, and context of language use.
2. To engage with pre-school age actors in activities and conversations to observe their use of language and conceptual understanding, ask open-ended questions and encourage children to explain their thoughts and actions.

3. To perform comparative multimodal analysis of artifacts created by the pre-school age actors alongside the verbal data acquired in course of observations. The analysis will draw on the principles of visual grammar and multimodal discourse analysis.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

There are no anticipated factors or limitations that will affect the distribution, or reuse of the scientific data generated. All research participants will be consented for broad data sharing. In addition to the research community, we expect these data will be used by practitioners and policymakers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Researchers will focus only on raw data because the study's goals don't require metadata analysis.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until research articles will be published.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

HML files are plain text files and they can be viewed using any text editor.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-12-31

The utility of the data might diminish over time due to contextual changes.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Project manager and the project team will be responsible for day-to-day oversight of data management activities and data sharing. Project manager will meet monthly with the project team to ensure the timeliness of data entry and review data to ensure the quality of data entry.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Will be covered by project funding.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Tija Ziriņa (0000-0002-5046-7675)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

These costs will be covered through a combination of institutional support and grant funding.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Only authorized individuals have access to data by using strong password practices - complex passwords that include a mix of uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and special characters.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

Direct Identifier Removal - eliminate obvious personal identifiers such as names and surnames and replace identifiers with codes.

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